

Fungicidal and Bactericidal Studies of Some Hydrazones. Part I

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Several substituted benzophenone nicotiny- and isonicotiny-hydrazones have been prepared and tested for their activities on *Aspergillus niger* and *S. aureus*.

In the present investigation several substituted benzoylbenzoic acids have been prepared by the decomposition of phenolphthaleins through oxime formation (Hubacher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 718) and fluoresceins by alkali fusion (Baeyer, *Annalen*, 1876, **23**, 183). The acids thus obtained have been condensed with isonicotinic and nicotinic acid hydrazides. The hydrazones thus produced have been tested for their fungicidal activity on *Aspergillus niger* and bacteriostatic activity on *S. aureus* by tube dilution method. The minimum concentrations of these for complete inhibition in 2 c.c. of the medium are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

R =		R' =	
Compound.	Conc. for complete inhibition of <i>A. niger.</i> <i>S. aureus.</i>	Compound.	Conc. for complete inhibition of <i>A. niger.</i> <i>S. aureus.</i>
R-	12.500 mg. 1.562 mg.	R'-	Nil 1.562 mg.
R-	3.125 0.781	R'-	6.250 mg. 0.781
R-	Nil 1.562	R'-	1.562 1.562
R-	3.125 1.562	R'-	6.250 3.125

Isonicotinic and nicotinic acid hydrazides are known to possess little or no fungicidal properties (F. W. Bieberdorf, "Antibiotic and Chemotherapy", 1953, vol. 3, pp. 513-20).

The present investigation indicates that their hydrazones with substituted benzoylbenzoic acids show some fungicidal properties. As expected, these hydrozones also possess bactericidal properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Hydroxy-2'-carboxybenzophenone Isonicotinyldiazone.—2-(4-Hydroxy)benzoylbenzoic acid (2.42 g.) was refluxed for 3 hours with isonicotinic acid hydrazide (1.37 g.) in ethanol (10 c.c.). After cooling, the crystals were filtered, washed with a little cold ethanol, and recrystallised from 60-80% ethanol when light yellow crystals of the hydrazone, m.p. 145°, was obtained in 60% yield. (Found: N, 11.46. $C_{20}H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.63%). It develops a violet colour with aqueous NaOH and effervesces with $NaHCO_3$. Other benzophenone isonicotinyldiazones, prepared in the same way, are recorded in Table II. All the compounds effervesce with $NaHCO_3$.

TABLE II

2'-Carboxybenzophenone isonicotinyldiazones.

Isonicotinic acid hydrazide taken = 1.37g.

Compound.	Benzoylbenzoic acid.	Colour.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		Colour with NaOH.
						Found.	Calc.	
2,4-Dihydroxy-	2-(2,4-Dihydroxy)- (2.58g.)	Dirty white	66%	170°	$C_{20}H_{15}O_5N_3$	11.38	11.14	Light yellow
3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-	2-(3-Methyl-4- hydroxy)- (2.56g.)	Pinkish white	45	150°	$C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_3$	11.63	11.20	Violet
2-Methyl-4-hydroxy- 5-propyli-	2-(2-Methyl-4- hydroxy-5-propyli)- (2.98g.)	Chocolate needles	50	173°	$C_{24}H_{23}O_4N_3$	10.12	10.07	Blue

4-Hydroxy-2'-carboxybenzophenone Nicotinyldiazone.—2-(4-Hydroxy)benzoylbenzoic acid (2.42 g.) and nicotinic acid hydrazide (1.37 g.) gave pinkish white crystals in 68% yield, m.p. 140°. (Found N, 11.44. $C_{20}H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.63%). It develops a violet colour with NaOH and effervesces with $NaHCO_3$. Other benzophenone derivatives prepared from nicotinic acid hydrazide (1.37 g.) are recorded in Table III. All the products effervesce with $NaHCO_3$.

TABLE III

2'-Carboxybenzophenone nicotinyldiazones.

Compound.	Benzoylbenzoic acid.	Colour.	Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		Colour with NaOH.
						Found.	Calc.	
2,4-Dihydroxy-	2-(2,4-Dihydroxy)- (2.58 g.)	Yellow	45%	160°	$C_{20}H_{15}O_5N_3$	11.29	11.14	Yellow
3-Methyl-4-hydroxy-	2-(3-Methyl- 4-hydroxy)- (2.56 g.)	Pink	37	140°	$C_{21}H_{17}O_4N_3$	11.06	11.20	Violet
2-Methyl-4-hydroxy- 5-propyli-	2-(2-Methyl-4-hydroxy- 5-propyli)- (2.98 g.)	White	48	160°	$C_{24}H_{23}O_4N_3$	10.36	10.07	Yellow

Fungicidal and Bacteriostatic Studies

For testing of fungicidal activities of the compounds, potato—glucose medium was used and for the testing of bacterial activity nutrient broth medium containing beef extract and peptone was used. *Aspergillus niger* and *S. aureus* respectively were used for this purpose; 2 c.c. of the medium was taken in each of the ten tubes. To the first tube 2 c.c. of a solution of a compound containing 0.0625 g./10 c.c. was added; 2 c.c. of this mixture was withdrawn and added to the second tube and the process continued to 9th tube. The tenth tube contained only the medium. The tubes were inoculated with a 24 hours' grown culture. The concentrations at which there was complete inhibition was recorded.

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